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BOARD CHARACTERISTICS, SDGS DISCLOSURE, AND FIRM PERFORMANCE: A CONCEPTUAL EXPLORATION OF MEDIATING EFFECTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the role of Board of Directors (BOD) characteristics in firm value creation, with a particular focus on the potential mediating role of Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) disclosure. The research aims to examine how BOD traits such as age, education, and experience may influence financial performance, as well as whether SDG disclosure enhances accountability and business outcomes. Drawing on Resource-Based Theory (RBT), the paper discusses the growing importance of transparency and sustainable governance practices, particularly in the context of firms listed on Bursa Malaysia. By investigating the link between BOD characteristics and firm performance, this conceptual paper provides insights into the evolving relationship between corporate governance and sustainability, offering directions for future empirical research.

Keywords: Board of Directors Characteristics, Corporate governance, Sustainable Development Goals, Resource-Based Theory, Firm Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Corporate governance (CG) is a cornerstone of long-term value creation and business performance. The Board of Directors (BOD) plays a central role in shaping strategy, overseeing risk, and promoting sustainability. In Malaysia, recent governance reforms—such as the Malaysian Code on Corporate Governance (MCCG) 2021—have encouraged firms to integrate sustainability into their structures, in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). While past research has examined how BOD characteristics like age, education, and experience relate to firm performance, the findings remain mixed, indicating the need to explore additional influencing factors.

At the same time, there is growing attention on SDG disclosure as a mechanism to improve governance transparency and accountability. However, the extent to which these disclosures strengthen the connection between board attributes and performance is still unclear. Guided by Resource-Based Theory (RBT), this paper conceptually examines whether board characteristics can enhance firm performance and whether SDG disclosure plays a mediating role in that relationship. Focusing on listed firms in Malaysia's consumer product and service sector, this paper offers a

foundation for future research by linking governance dynamics with sustainability disclosure.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Prior research has explored how individual board attributes influence financial outcomes, but evidence remains inconclusive. For example, board age has been associated with stronger governance and sustainability orientation, as older directors often bring seasoned judgment and experience (Beji et al., 2021). Educational diversity among directors has also shown potential in enhancing firm transparency and improving sustainability disclosure practices (Katmon et al., 2019). Likewise, director experience contributes to better strategic oversight and alignment with stakeholder expectations, which can translate into improved performance (Saidu, 2019). Within the Malaysian context, reforms such as the MCCG 2021 have underscored the importance of integrating sustainability into governance practices. This has led firms to place greater emphasis on aligning their disclosures with the SDGs. These developments raise the question of whether SDG disclosure acts as a bridge between board characteristics and financial performance. Grounded in RBT, which positions human capital and sustainability initiatives as valuable internal resources (Grant, 1991), this research examines how the composition of the board may contribute to performance in a setting increasingly shaped by sustainability imperatives.

3. METHODOLOGY

This research adopts a quantitative approach using secondary data from firms listed on Bursa Malaysia's Main Market between 2018 and 2022. Financial data, including Return on Equity (ROE), and Board of Directors' characteristics—age, education, and experience—were collected from annual, integrated, and sustainability reports. Content analysis was conducted to extract relevant information, particularly regarding SDG disclosures, based on the SDG Global Indicator Framework. The sample focuses on the Consumer Products and Services sector, identified as a key contributor to Malaysia's gross domestic product (GDP) (iFAST Research Team, 2021; Ministry of Finance Malaysia, 2022)

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This section outlines the conceptual basis of the research and discusses its anticipated contributions to corporate governance and sustainability literature.

4.1 Discussion

This concept paper outlines a two-phase exploration of the relationship between BOD characteristics—age, education, and experience—and firm performance, with a specific focus on the role of SDGs disclosure. The first phase examines the direct relationship between BOD characteristics and firm performance, while the second phase investigates whether SDGs disclosure mediates this relationship. It is hypothesized that SDGs disclosure will have a significant mediating effect, facilitating the translation of board characteristics into performance outcomes. However, it is likely that many firms, especially in the Consumer Products and Services sector, currently treat SDGs disclosure as a compliance-driven exercise rather than a strategic, performance-enhancing tool. This exploration aims to assess the integration of SDGs disclosure within governance frameworks and its influence on firm performance, considering both direct and mediated effects.

4.2 Conclusion

This concept paper proposes a comprehensive framework for understanding the role of BOD characteristics and SDGs disclosure in shaping firm performance. The expected findings suggest that while BOD characteristics such as age, education, and experience may have a direct relationship with performance, their impact is likely enhanced—or mediated—through SDGs disclosure. As SDGs disclosure becomes increasingly relevant, it is anticipated that its integration within CG mechanisms

could significantly influence firm performance, providing both direct and indirect pathways for value creation.

Future research could expand on this framework by empirically testing the hypothesized relationships across different industries and governance structures. Researchers may also explore alternative measures of sustainability integration, moving beyond disclosure to examine firms' strategies for embedding SDGs into their operations. Furthermore, exploring the influence of other governance mechanisms, such as executive compensation or board diversity, could deepen the understanding of how governance factors impact sustainability outcomes. A broader sample size or industry-specific focus could also offer more generalizable insights into the role of SDGs in governance and performance.

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